

ABOUT THE IMPORTANCE OF ETIQUETTE IN THE PEDAGOGICAL SPHERE

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Abstract: The discipline "Professional Ethics" is important in the formation of future teachers' pedagogical ethics because it includes not only the study of theoretical foundations of professional and pedagogical ethics, but also the analysis of relevant regulatory documents such as the code of professional ethics of the teacher, the ethical code of the teacher, the code of honor and service of the teacher, the professional code ethics and official behavior of a teacher, and so on. Professional regulatory materials should illustrate to students the requirement to conform with ethical standards and rules of behavior in order to enter the professional community and, more importantly, for professional growth.

Keywords: ethical code, pedagogical politeness, motivation, moral teaching, and behavioral culture.

Introduction

«Our manners, like our faces, even the most beautiful ones, should be different from each other» (Anthony Eigley Cooper Shaftesbury).

Etiquette is a collection of socially acceptable behavioral guidelines. These norms changed greatly over the history of human civilization. However, these regulations differ from those that are now approved during each era. A teacher is someone whose professional field is connected to teaching. He interacts with others while performing his tasks. They are professionals and scholars. As a result, it is critical for a teacher to

have information as well as the capacity to impart it to others. Other factors should be considered by the instructor as well. Communication, behavior, and appearance are all competent and respectful.

All of these principles are referred to together as educational etiquette. A teacher is more than simply a teacher at school or at other educational institution; he or she is also a mentor in everyone's life. After all, the profession is basically one, yet it offers variety of purposes! This is a doctor, a psychologist, a motivator, a mother and father, and the instructor himself all mixed into one. To become a teacher, you must go through a lot of training and be able to do a little bit of everything, if not more. They began testing the building of a robot instructor in this age of current technology. The culture of behavior of a teacher not only depends on social foundations, but also has an impact on them. The educator and the school teacher form a culture of behavior among their pupils, and also influence the culture of behavior of the parents of the pupils. A college or university teacher improves the culture of behavior of future teachers. Such an indirect impact of the teacher on society seems to us quite significant.

Literature review: The article reveals and shows the topic of teacher etiquette. Summing up, we can say that the teacher, based on research, builds and gives the foundation to the child. He must be educated himself in order to educate others. The very first teachers in a person's life are his parents, who not only give life, but also invest the knowledge necessary for life, instill moral concepts and values accepted in human society. Teachers laid the foundations for the further development of abilities; subsequently, for eleven years, it is teachers at school who provide the main information base in various fields of knowledge.

Research methodology: In the research were used various scientific articles, as well as books on the psychology and methodology of the teacher. Books of different languages were used. Newspapers, magazines and scholarly articles were used and the collected ideas were written and discussed.

Analysis and results: The theme was discussed and only the main important reasons and details were discussed and written.

Within the framework of a huge social group - educators, teachers, teachers of educational institutions - rules of conduct are also developed, united in pedagogical etiquette. When characterizing the communicative behavior of a teacher, such properties as the tone of speech, the manner of addressing students, answering them, the justification for using value judgments, the nature of facial expressions, movements, and gestures accompanying what is said are very important. It is very important in what tone the teacher speaks; that the same phrase can be pronounced fifty ways.

However, the application of theoretical information about speech etiquette and the rules of the culture of pedagogical communication in practice causes certain difficulties. Various minor misunderstandings and quarrels, daily conflicts, sudden crisis situations require a correct and effective response from the teacher.

Sometimes teachers break into a raised tone or even scream, explaining that the teacher is “also a person.” “Also human” is not an excuse; this kind of behavior is a sign of his professional incompetence.

About behavior in an educational institution. Always remember that not only children are around you, but also teenagers, adults. You should not quickly walk along the corridor, unnecessarily afraid of representatives of the administration. Be collected, polite and courteous.

There are several general rules of business etiquette for a teacher:

1. Punctuality. You need to be able to calculate the time required to arrive or come to work on time. As a rule, it is advisable for the teacher to do this no later than 15-20 minutes before the start of the lesson.

2. Composure and accuracy. The rhythm of pedagogical work requires special concentration from the teacher, order on the desktop, in a business briefcase or in a bag.

3. Don't talk too much. Every organization has its secrets, and in the classroom it is customary to behave courteously, but without unnecessary talk.

4. Good language of communication. Remember that it is the teacher that characterizes clean and competent speech.

5. Ability to communicate. This is art, and in an educational institution with your colleagues, students and their parents - doubly art!

6. Appearance of the teacher. Remember, dozens of eyes of people of all ages look at you every minute: respect “yourself in yourself”, but also do not forget that you are just a woman or a man (slenderness, gait, appearance, ability to present yourself, and so on). In any situation, you must look the right way. And yet, pedagogical ethics implies special requirements for the teacher's clothing.

However, the main thing is the authority of the teacher, his position in the eyes of colleagues, the administration of the educational institution, students of this age category, parents of students.

The authority of the teacher is a special professional position that determines the influence on students, gives the right to make decisions, express assessments, and give advice. The true authority of a teacher-educator is based not on official and age privileges, but on high personal and professional qualities: a democratic style of cooperation with pupils, the ability to communicate openly, his desire for continuous

improvement, erudition, competence, fairness and kindness, common culture, etc. n. True authority is that attitude of the students towards the teacher which encourages the students to be the teacher's junior companions.

An important role in this is played by the high level of professional competence of the teacher, deep intelligence, personal citizenship. In general, when the words of one excellent writer: "Everything in a person should be beautiful: both the face, and clothes, and the soul, and thoughts" are combined with high professionalism and philanthropy, then the teacher can count on pedagogical authority.

Etiquette is a set of rules of conduct that regulate the external manifestation of human relationships. Business etiquette regulates the behavior of people related to the performance of their official duties. Secular - streamlines communication in the field of leisure. In addition to the rules of etiquette, there is professional etiquette for everyone. There are relationships in life that provide the highest efficiency in the performance of a professional function. In a particular team, a group of workers, certain traditions develop, which over time acquire the strength of moral principles and constitute the etiquette of this group. In the practice of business relations there are always some standard situations that cannot be avoided. For these situations, they develop forms and rules of behavior. This set of rules constitutes the etiquette of business communication. Business etiquette includes strict adherence to the rules of a culture of behavior, which implies, first of all, a deep respect for human individuality. The social role played by this or that person should not be self-sufficient. A cultured person should show sincere respect to everyone. An essential feature of the culture of behavior of any person is following speech etiquette, i.e. the use of a system of nationally specific stereotypes, stable communication formulas designed to establish and maintain contacts and the chosen tone.

The moral basis of the teacher's speech behavior is humanism, a polite, respectful, tolerant attitude towards the personality of the student, regardless of his age, academic performance and behavior. Typical communicative situations, etiquette expressions are: appeal, greeting, acquaintance, apology, gratitude, congratulations, invitation, request, advice, warning, approval, compliment, farewell.

Speech etiquette provides a culture of inclusion, maintenance, switching the attention of the interlocutor, ending contact, expressing gratitude, agreement, disagreement, satisfaction, regret, sympathy, etc. The decisive stages of communication with the audience are the entry into contact, its maintenance and termination. The traditional politeness formulas "Hello, guys" or "Good afternoon, friends" carry a certain psychological and pedagogical load. With their help, the teacher

infects the trainees with an optimistic attitude, sets the necessary tone for communication - purely business, work or friendly. The value of "speech tuning" in establishing contacts between interlocutors is known. The exchange of seemingly insignificant questions and remarks about health, mood, weather, etc. allows you to look at each other, feel the emotional state, adequately perceive the communicative situation and choose the necessary communication tactics.

There is a similarity between the professional skills of a teacher and an actor, since the object of their influence is the spiritual world of the individual, and the main means is speech expression. The high level of its development is characterized as artistic, i.e. skillful, masterful, virtuoso. Each teacher widely uses for pedagogical purposes a gaze, a reproachful shake of the head, a smile or a distressed facial expression, gestures of affirmation and denial. Expressive is not only lively facial expressions and energetic gestures, but also a state of static, bodily immobility. Intentionally prolonged pause and even coughing help students to better understand the teacher. The culture of speech behavior involves the teacher's understanding of his expressive manifestations, their critical self-assessment, the cultivation of the natural identity of the language and its conscious use for educational purposes. Unfortunately, many teachers have noticed the stereotype of emotional self-expression. And more expressive are not positive, but negative feelings shown in relation to the trainees. The means of expressiveness is figurativeness, the metaphorical nature of the word, i.e., the operation of speech forms that have a figurative meaning. Appropriately used sayings, proverbs, phraseological units, winged words help the teacher clearly and concisely express thoughts and feelings. The value of non-verbal communications is extremely high. They can perform all the basic functions of linguistic signs and actually replace spoken language.

In addition to supplementing, substituting, anticipating a word, regulating, focusing attention on one or another part of the statement, non-verbal expression saves speech means. Non-verbal expression has priority in creating the image of the speaker, reflecting the experienced emotions and feelings - excitement and indifference, confidence and doubt, sympathy and antipathy, joy and anger.

An important role is played by the manners of the teacher, which consist of gait, body movements, posture when sitting, standing, gesticulation, facial expressions. A special role in the transfer of information during the lesson is given to facial expressions - the movements of the muscles of the face. Facial expressions help to express lived states, relationships.

Studies have shown that if the teacher's face is motionless, up to 10-15% of information is lost. Avoid looking at walls, windows, and ceilings. The teacher's gaze should be turned to the students, creating visual contact. At the same time, you need to

strive to keep the entire audience in sight. The gloomy, gloomy expression of the teacher's face depresses the students, causes them a feeling of hostility.

A stony, insensitive facial expression alienates them from the teacher, causes embarrassment and unwillingness to ask questions, go to consultations and additional classes. An important element of facial expression is a smile, which without words shows the joy and pleasure of communication. However, the smile of the teacher should be natural and express his true feelings. Sometimes there are on-duty insensitive smiles that mask the true essence of a person.

Such smiles may not be immediately recognized, however, once recognized, they cause a deep and persistent distrust of the smiling person. The teacher should not abuse the "smiling", in this case, the students develop an opinion about the falsity of the teacher's behavior. There must be a good, understandable reason for the smile to appear. But, of course, you need to understand that the point is not so much in a smile, but in the inner desire of the teacher to understand each student, his needs and condition.

In addition to the above, often a teacher, being carried away by communication, loses control over his body movements and, at the same time, can damage his authority. In psychology, there are concepts of "openness" and "closeness" of the interlocutor. Openness consists in a person's disposition to communication, attentive perception of information, and the desire to understand the interlocutor. Closeness is a state that makes communication difficult and leads to misunderstanding between interlocutors. It is unacceptable for the teacher to use any gestures of insult and threat.

Also, when calling a student to answer, it is unacceptable to poke a pointer at the child. The movement of the teacher to the sides from the window to the door is not recommended, it is better to walk around the office back and forth. It is also necessary to remember about the distance, not to invade the personal space of schoolchildren. For communication at work, a distance that does not go beyond the personal zone is acceptable. In order not to spoil the impression of yourself, it is recommended not to point your finger at a person or object; during a conversation, do not slap the students on the shoulder, twist the buttons on their clothes, do not grab the sleeve; twisting various objects in your hands, drumming your fingers on the table, crunching your fingers, scratching, rummaging through your pockets.

The teacher should restrain his negative emotions; he should not have a raised tone. Compliance with simple rules of etiquette increases the authority of the teacher in the eyes of students, contributes to the harmonization of their relationship.

Pedagogical ethics provides for the love and respect of the teacher for students, as well as a similar attitude of students towards the teacher. Indirectly, through the

learning process, the teacher takes care of the well-being of students in the areas of their communication with each other. A real teacher himself is a highly moral person, and therefore he combines kindness and politeness with high demands, excludes violence and coercion from the arsenal of means of influencing students. A real teacher is characterized by kindness, restraint, politeness, which are not a formal obligation, but a need for him. Teachers, in turn, win respect and love of students by honest work. First, the authority of power acts, and then the authority of power passes into the power of authority, if the teacher is a master of his craft, a moral person. The power of authority is an irresistible and reliable force.

A teacher, by his very purpose and social status, must always be a sculptor of the morality of young people, teach them to feel, understand, think, respect a person in a person, influence students not with separate methods, exercises, but with his whole being. Any violation on his part of even a petty moral principle plunges him into an abyss of distrust in the eyes of the students. In a teacher, everything should be natural, no fake, otherwise sooner or later there will be a collapse. The teacher communicates with his audience for a long time and quite closely, and as a rule, he fails to deceive her with hypocrisy, demagoguery. The most reasonable and most effective line of his behavior in the process of moral education is the desire to be as natural as possible. If the teacher has shortcomings that students should not know about, then the only sure way to hide them is to overcome them in oneself, otherwise, most likely, students will “bite through” insincerity. Often, the naturalness of the teacher's behavior smooths out small deviations from the accepted norms of behavior in the eyes of students. Naturalness, therefore, is a strong tool that acts in favor of the teacher.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that pedagogical ethics is based not only on love for students, but also on a deep knowledge and understanding of their inner world, goals, interests and aspirations, character traits of each student, on the pedagogy of cooperation. It should be taught in such a way that the student really becomes an accomplice in the learning process. If you do not make the student your ally, then no moral influence can be exerted on him. Only by introducing a student to active creative and independent activity, knowing and understanding him, it is possible to contribute to the moral formation of future specialists.

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